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SALTOpower

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1. INTRODUCTION

In fulfilment of SALTOpower¹ Grant Agreement on the obligations of the Consortium towards the Project Owner (PO) regarding project deliverables, the current document stands as Deliverable D3.3 - Career attractiveness framework report, as described in the project Description of Action (Part A).

This Deliverable reports on the implementation and impacts of career attractiveness support measures:

- ERC Facility: description of support assets, identified candidates for Advanced and Synergy Grants, abstract of submitted proposals, outcome of submitted proposals;
- Spin-Off facility: description of support assets, asset matrix per partner, IP paths and foreseeable costs, company creation path and foreseeable costs and incentives, HR rules for transition to Spin-Off, Spin-Off creation framework in UEvora, blueprint for creation of spin-off (based on JRA result or on virtual result inspired in JRA);
- Living Amenities Facility: description of approach (web based platform), description of related initiatives, statistics, satisfaction inquiries, replication in TOP partners.

The activities described in this D3.3 are within the framework of Work Package (WP) 3.

2. CAREER ATTRACTIVENESS IN THE FRAMEWORK OF SALTOPower PROJECT

Addressing one of the objectives of SALTOpower, “3. To steer Career Building and attractiveness of Young Researchers to UEvora”, different support measures have been implemented in the project, aiming at a holistic approach to an attractiveness framework able to create lasting impacts in the Widening institution.

Rendering the Widening institution - the University of Évora - attractive to young researchers and, especially, creating an attractiveness framework, is surely related to the quality of research and research infrastructure therein available, but encompasses also other research unrelated aspects pertaining to the institution, the city, and the region.

Whereas research related aspects have been addressed by specific support actions on:

- capacity building, with SALTOpower Fast-Track Schools (see related Deliverable 3.1);
- tutoring and mentoring of PhD students and young researchers (see related Deliverable 3.2);
- fostering young researchers into leadership positions, with the development of the ERC Facility,

all of them grounded in SALTOpower concrete research focus and on its Joint Research Activity, an additional set of support actions has been envisaged as to widen SALTOpower attractiveness framework.

An assessment of “regional attractiveness” indicators to the region where the Widening institution is located² provides an interesting starting point. The definition of ‘regional attractiveness’ indicators has been developed as a tool for analysing the structural reasons for unequal development between regions, at supra- and infra-national level. Going beyond the criteria used in different methodologies for establishing these indicators, centred on parameters such as Foreign Direct Investment, the export index or the ‘brain drain’, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) recently developed a holistic methodology for

¹ Project: 101079303 — SALTOpower — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

² Horta, P., Rosmaninho N., “Atractividade de Recursos Humanos Qualificados para a Região do Alentejo: aspectos críticos para uma estratégia de atractividade regional” (*Attractiveness of Qualified Human Resources to the Alentejo Region: critical aspects for a regional attractiveness strategy*). Public Policy Portuguese Journal, Volume 8, Number 2 (2023). University of Évora, UMPP.

quantifying a Regional Attractiveness Index (RAI). Based on six core dimensions - Economic Attractiveness, Natural Environment, Connectivity, Residents' Well-being, Space and Housing, Visitor Attractiveness - this methodology produces results relating to the attractiveness of three types of agents: Investors, Visitors and Talent³.

Taking the attractiveness index produced by this methodology as a starting point for a general assessment of the territory as an attractor of investment and talent (not neglecting the dimension of Visitors as an element of diversity and valorisation of heritage assets normally associated with tourism activity), the Better Life Index (BLI) also produced by the OECD⁴, provides an indication of the quality of life of residents.

Aimed at comparing conditions of 'well-being' between countries, this index is based on eleven parameters in the field of material conditions and quality of life: housing, income, employment, community, education, environment, civic participation, health, personal satisfaction, security and work-life balance.

In this study², the results obtained for the RAI and BLI serve as the basis for an analysis of the region's deficits in a) attracting and b) retaining talent, not only for the Alentejo region, but also for the neighbouring regions, possibly competing for talent: the Metropolitan Region of Lisbon and the Algarve.

Results for the different parameters assessed in each of these indicators, for both Alentejo and the neighbouring (competing) regions, are summarized in Figure 2.1.

This study shows the region's competitive advantages over its competitors:

- the natural environment/environment and;
- space/security and housing conditions,

aspects that will need to be highlighted and capitalised on, pointing out as disadvantages:

- the economic attractivity;
- the well-being of residents / civic participation, education, health;
- connectivity/access to services and;
- the attractiveness of visitors / cultural offer.

Addressing (at least some of) these dimensions of attractiveness, SALTOpower encompassed additional support measures, such as the development of:

- the "Spin-off Facility", aiming at improving economic attractiveness conditions by means of supporting an "entrepreneurship path" to the further development of young researchers' careers by means of their exploitation of research results;
- the "Living Amenities Facility", aiming at improving well being, access to services and cultural offer aspects or at capitalizing the region's advantages on natural environment or space, security and housing conditions.

³ OECD Regional Development Papers No. 36: Measuring the attractiveness of regions. OECD, 2022. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1787/fbe44086-en>

⁴ OECD Better Life Index. <https://www.oecdbetterlifeindex.org>

□PT18: Alentejo □PT17: Área Metropolitana de Lisboa □PT15: Algarve

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.1: Classification on the different parameters of (a) Regional Attractiveness Index (RAI)⁵ and (b) Better Life Index (BLI)⁶ for the regions of Alentejo and Algarve compared to the reference Lisbon Metropolitan Area (Ref.100).

⁵ *TRACT. ECONÓMICA*: economic attractiveness; *AMBIENTE NATURAL*: natural environment; *CONECTIVIDADE*: connectivity; *BEM-ESTAR RESID.*: residents well being; *ESPAÇO E HABITAÇÃO*: site and housing; *TRACT. VISITANTES*: attractiveness to visitors

⁶ *Habitação*: housing; *Acesso a serviços*: access to services; *Segurança*: safety; *Satisfação pessoal*: personal satisfaction; *Saúde*: Health; *Participação Cívica*: civil participation; *Meio Ambiente*: Environment; *Comunidade*: community; *Educação*: education; *Emprego*: employment; *Rendimento*: income

3. CAPACITY BUILDING

Capacity building activities within SALTOpower included not only training activities, in the form of “Fast-Track Schools” aimed not only at CYR and YR but also to Industry engineers and technicians, but also Tutoring activities, aimed at supporting the development of PhD works by CYR, and Mentoring activities, aimed at supporting the career development of YR including at the development of leadership skills. These activities have been supported by Mobility activities, promoting the exchange of CYR and YR among the research infrastructure of all the partners in the Consortium.

3.1. Fast-track Schools

Aimed not only at CYR and YR but also at Industry engineers and technicians, the three editions of the Fast-track Schools (FTS), duly reported in SALTOpower D3.1, were an evolutionary training along the project focused on the following main content approach:

1. Molten salt basic research topics and State-of-the-Art, in May 2023, in ENEA Casaccia Research Centre in Rome, with 59 attendees (Figure 3.1);
2. Molten salt experimental procedures and implementation, in July 2024, in DLR Research Centre Cologne, with 51 attendees (Figure 3.2);
3. Technology benchmarking and Exploitation, in November 2024, at the University of Évora, with 44 attendees (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.1: FTS #1 - Rome.

Figure 3.2: FTS #2 - Cologne.

Figure 3.3: FTS #3 - Évora.

Satisfaction surveys delivered to the attendees in the three editions of the FTS showed an overall satisfaction rate of 4.36 out of 5.

FTS materials are publicly available and described in Deliverable 3.1 - Fast-Track School Materials.

3.2. Tutoring and mentoring

Task 3.2 Tutoring, led by DLR, to support the Candidate Young Researchers (CYRs) to develop a PhD thesis in the scope of SALTOpower, including CYR mobilities from the Widening partner (UÉvora) to the TOP partners (ENEA and DLR) in a total of 5,6 weeks by M29. Six CYRs have been engaged in the project, as presented in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Engagement of CYR in SALTOpower

Partner	CYR name	PhD topic [JRA Task and guidance]	Tutor [Partner] Co-tutor [Partner]
UEVORA	Tiago Eusébio	Competitiveness of CBs in power generation and industrial applications [T2.2 Radia Cadi]	Pedro Horta [UEVORA] Reiner Buck, Thomas Bauer [DLR]
UEVORA	João Marchã	Technical and Economic Feasibility of Green Hydrogen Production from Agricultural Waste: An Approach via Thermochemical Processes with Solar Integration [T2.1 Diogo Canavarro]	Pedro Horta [UEVORA] Michela Lanchi, Luca Turcheti [ENEA]
UEVORA	Junior Mané	Numerical simulation of thermocline tanks based on different operating concepts and stratification strategies	Pedro Horta [UEVORA] Nuno Domingues [NOVA] Isabel Malico [UEVORA]
ENEA	Matteo Battaglia	Theoretical and experimental analysis of green hydrogen production processes and storage materials coupling with CSP technology	Anna Chiara Tizzoni, Salvatore Sau [ENEA]
DLR	Markus Reichart	Gas-particle direct-contact trickle-flow heat-exchanger for application in concentrated solar tower systems [T2.2]	Robert Pitz-Paal, Reiner Buck [DLR]
DLR	Nithaarshini Sritharen	Power-to-heat methods with molten salt technologies [T2.2]	Robert Pitz-Paal, Jana Stengler [DLR]

Task 3.3 Mentoring, led by ENEA, supports Young Researchers (YR) engaged in SALTOpower JRA and FTS, aiming at their career development towards team leaders/leading researchers in the SALTOpower field, including mobilities of UÉvora YR to TOP partners of 5 weeks by M29. Table 3.2 summarizes the SALTOpower YR engagement.

Table 3.2: Engagement of YR in SALTOpower

Partner	YR name	JRA Task	Mentor at Host Mentor [Partner]
UEVORA	Diogo Canavarro	T2.1	Pedro Horta Michela Lanchi, Luca Turcheti [ENEA] Martin Roeb, Clarice Lorreyette [DLR]
UEVORA	Radia Ait El Cadi	T2.2	Pedro Horta [UEVORA] Reiner Buck, Thomas Bauer [DLR]
UEVORA	Asma Noura	T2.1	Pedro Horta, Diogo Canavarro [UEVORA] Michela Lanchi, Luca Turcheti [ENEA] Clarisse Lorreyette [DLR]
UEVORA	Imen Amri	T2.1	Pedro Horta, Diogo Canavarro [UEVORA] Michela Lanchi, Luca Turcheti [ENEA] Clarisse Lorreyette [DLR]
ENEA	Marco D'Auria	T2.2	Michela Lanchi [ENEA] Reiner Buck, Thomas Bauer [DLR]
ENEA	Francesco Aldo Rovense	T2.2	Michela Lanchi [ENEA] Reiner Buck, Thomas Bauer [DLR]
ENEA	Anna Chiara Tizzoni	T2.1	Luca Turcheti [ENEA] Martin Roeb, Clarice Lorreyette [DLR]
ENEA	Mattia Cagnoli	T2.2	Michela Lanchi [ENEA] Reiner Buck, Thomas Bauer [DLR]

A survey was conducted during the last project meeting (November 2024) to assess the SALTOpower team's satisfaction, and a total of 6 answers were received from CYR and YR. Table 3.3 presents some of the more relevant questions answered by CYR and YR, and to which they gave a score from 1 to 5 where: 1 means "I'm completely unsatisfied", 2 means "I'm partially unsatisfied", 3 means "I'm not satisfied or unsatisfied", 4 means "I'm partially satisfied" and 5 means "I completely satisfied".

Table 3.3: SALTOpower CYR and YR answers to the satisfaction survey

Question	Classification (out of 5)
How satisfied are you with SALTOpower research?	4,33
How satisfied are you with the support for career development at your institution?	3,67
How satisfied are you with the SALTOpower Research Infrastructure?	4,17
How satisfied are you with the SALTOpower team?	5,00
How satisfied are you with SALTOpower in general?	4,33

Adding to mentoring activities aimed at YR, leadership training has also been sought to provide YR with tools and resources supporting the objective of hosting their careers to a group leadership position.

A leadership training will take place with the UÉvora team, including SALTOpower's YR and CYR, in May 2025. The programme is presented in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4: Program of Leadership Training to UEvora YR and CYR

Leadership 101 (1 day)		
06.05.2025		
9:00 - 9:30	Welcome and Introduction	Objectives: Introduction of the training and the participants Topics: Training objectives, agenda, introduction of participants
9:30 - 10:30	Activity 1 - Leadership Styles	Objectives: To identify each participant's leadership style and understand how it impacts the team. Topics: 4 classic leadership styles
10:30 - 11:15	Activity 2 - Task prioritisation	Objectives: Organise and prioritise tasks with a simple and intuitive matrix Topics: Eisenhower matrix
11:15 - 11:30	Break	
11:30 - 12:30	Activity 3 - Delegating with Efficiency and Confidence	Objectives: To delegate tasks effectively, ensuring quality results. Topics: Introduction to the principles of delegating tasks, RACI matrix
12:30 - 13:30	Lunch	
13:30 - 14:30	Activity 4 - Aligning Expectations and Feedback	Objectives: Improve communication and alignment between leadership and the team Topics: Guided role play of scenarios proposed by the participants.
14:30 - 15:15	Activity 5 - Motivation and Emotional Intelligence	Objectives: Identify factors that motivate the team and learn how to use them strategically Topics: Emotional intelligence and its impact on individual and team motivation
15:15 - 15:30	Break	
15:30 - 16:30	Activity 6 - Conflict Resolution in Practice	Objectives: To explore techniques for resolving conflicts constructively Topics: Conflict resolution
16:30 - 17:00	Closing and Final Reflection	Objectives: Reflection on the training and definition of next steps Topics: Making the connection between training content and practical work

4. ERC FACILITY

Regarded as one of the most prestigious career development support schemes for researchers in the European space, the Research Grants of the European Research Council⁷ are organized in four main categories following different career stages:

- ERC Starting Grant, for researchers with 2 to 7 years of postdoctoral experience;
- ERC Consolidator Grant, for researchers with 7 to 12 years of postdoctoral experience;

⁷ <https://erc.europa.eu/apply-grant>

- ERC Advanced Grant, for established research leaders, and;
- ERC Synergy Grant, for groups of 2 to 4 researchers combining skills and resources, tackling ambitious research challenges.

In the framework of SALTOpower, the application to ERC Grants has been sought as an instrument for exercising Young Researchers in the development of a career development plan, aiming at their future leadership of a research team developing activities aligned with the objectives of the SALTOpower Joint Research Activity.

To this end, information on ERC Grant applications has been conveyed, from a early stage in the project, to the Young Researchers engaged in the project, namely on available calls and proposal templates, besides due discussion of possible topics and development of proposals along the Mentoring activities and mobility actions developed in the project (Task 3.2).

Moreover, at the Widening institutions' side, YRs have been made acquainted with a specific support program recently made available through the Portuguese National Contact Point institution, FCT - Science and Technology Foundation, FCT's ERC Portugal Program⁸.

Aiming at increasing the national participation in the ERC Calls, this program provides support for the different stages of proposal submission: from preparing and evaluating applications, to training future applicants and attracting and retaining talent. The program has three axes: ERC-PT Pre-assessment, ERC-PT A-Projects and ERC-PT Careers.

ERC-PT Pre-assessment supports the national scientific community in preparing proposals to the ERC. It consists of a pre-assessment by peers at the proposal preparation stage, following international best practice and according to the ERC's assessment criteria. The process is conducted by a College of international evaluators, appointed annually and covering all scientific areas, with highly experienced profiles in evaluation processes, preferably with experience of several editions as ERC panel members. It culminates in suggestions for improving the proposal, which reflect the ERC's evaluation criteria and evaluator profiles. This axis has supported national applications in 3 ERC Calls. Despite being a very recent program, it already has applications that have been selected for funding or have reached the second stage of the evaluation process.

ERC-PT A-Projects, the first axis launched under this program, is an FCT funding line for national applications with a top evaluation and recommendation for funding by the ERC, but which do not obtain funding due to budget limitations. Applications with an 'A' rating in the Starting, Consolidator and Advanced grants typologies are eligible for this funding, and, from October 2024, also Synergy grants. This financial support, up to a maximum of 250,000 euros per application, is intended to enable the institutions of the National Science and Technology System (SNCT) and their researchers for future ERC applications. The application period is open until December 31, 2025.

ERC-PT Careers, launched in June 2024, promotes the attraction and retention of researchers with projects funded by ERC Calls, still in progress or completed in less than 2 years, for permanent positions in SNCT and Higher Education institutions. This axis is made up of two types: (i) ATTRACT, with funding of up to 550,000 euros, to host projects that are transferred from foreign institutions through open-ended contracts with their principal investigators; (ii) RETAIN, an incentive to recruit researchers already carrying out research in Portugal and with an ERC project active or completed less than 2 years ago, for permanent positions in SNCT or Higher Education institutions.

ERC-PT A Projects and ERC-PT Careers are funded by the Recovery and Resilience Plan (PRR), in the resilience dimension and in the "RE-C06-i06 - Science Plus Capacity Building" component.

⁸ <https://www.fct.pt/en/financiamento/programas-de-financiamento/programa-erc-portugal/>

Finally, an ERC Synergy Grant proposal has been sought as an instrument to align ideas and structure a follow-up strategy to SALTOpower scientific cooperation and research infrastructure development among Senior Researchers.

To this end, a number of specific meetings among Senior Researchers engaged in the project have been developed, aiming at identifying a suitable - and eligible - proposal encompassing not only the researchers' background complementarities but also the infrastructural synergies found among the Consortium partners.

4.1 ERC Starting Grant applications

Considering the eligibility criteria for applicants to ERC Starting Grants - researchers with 2 to 7 years of postdoctoral experience - the eligibility of Young Researchers enrolled in SALTOpower JRA, on the side of each of the Consortium partners, was checked, as illustrated in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Eligibility of YR in SALTOpower to ERC Starting Grant applications

Partner	YR name	JRA Task	Mentor at Host Mentor [Partner]	PhD year	Eligibility
UEVORA	Diogo Canavarro	T2.1	Pedro Horta Michela Lanchi, Luca Turcheti [ENEA] Martin Roeb, Clarisse Lorreyette [DLR]	2014	N
UEVORA	Radia Ait El Cadi	T2.2	Pedro Horta [UEVORA] Reiner Buck, Thomas Bauer [DLR]	2020	Y
UEVORA	Asma Nouira	T2.2	Pedro Horta, Diogo Canavarro [UEVORA] Michela Lanchi, Luca Turcheti [ENEA] Clarisse Lorreyette [DLR]	2023	Y
UEVORA	Imen Amri	T2.1	Pedro Horta, Diogo Canavarro [UEVORA] Michela Lanchi, Luca Turcheti [ENEA] Clarisse Lorreyette [DLR]	2022	Y
ENEA	Marco D'Auria	T2.2	Michela Lanchi Reiner Buck, Thomas Bauer [DLR]	2015	N
ENEA	Francesco Aldo Rovense	T2.2	Michela Lanchi Reiner Buck, Thomas Bauer [DLR]	2018	Y
ENEA	Anna Chiara Tizzoni	T2.1	Luca Turcheti Martin Roeb, Clarice Lorreyette [DLR]	2016	N

Out of the four eligible YRs, and exceeding the project target of 2 ERC Starting Grant proposals, one ERC Starting Grant application has already been submitted to the 2024 Call submitted and three are under preparation, for submission in the 2025 Call, as follows.

SALTOpower YR Francesco Aldo Rovense has submitted an ERC Starting Grant proposal on 15 October 2024, after the description in Table 4.2. Assessment results for step 1 are expected by 5 May 2025, and step 2 by 22 August 2025.

Table 4.2: Summary of ERC Starting Grant application by Francesco Aldo Rovense (ENEA YR)

Call	
Applicant name	Francesco Aldo Rovense
Title	External magnetic Field Enhancing Stability of thermal energy sTOrage - EFESTO
Abstract	<p>Sedimentation of nanoparticles presents a major challenge for thermal energy storage systems employing nanoparticle-enhanced phase change materials (NEPCM). These systems use nanoparticles to enhance certain properties of phase change materials (PCMs), such as specific heat and thermal conductivity. However, the sedimentation issue, which is also linked to problems caused by aggregation due to van der Waals intermolecular forces, diminishes the benefits of adding nanoparticles, as they tend to settle at the vessel bottom due to gravitational forces after several melting and solidification cycles. As a result, they are not uniformly dispersed throughout the storage volume. Methods such as mechanical and ultrasonic agitation, along with the use of surfactants, fail to resolve this issue. The EFESTO project aims to explore a novel method to enhance the stability of NEPCM by using a magnetic field to address the sedimentation of ferromagnetic nanoparticles, keeping them in suspension while preventing their aggregation. To meet the research objectives of the EFESTO project, the preliminary phase will involve selecting the most suitable nanoparticles and PCMs exploitable in NEPCM-based thermal energy storage systems, where magnetic fields can effectively manage nanoparticle sedimentation without causing aggregation. Two prototypes of the storage systems, one at the microscale and another at a broader laboratory scale, along with their related experimental setups, will be established to study the behaviour of ferromagnetic nanoparticles in NEPCM under the influence of magnetic fields. Numerical models will be developed to simulate the magnetic field's management of sedimentation and aggregation phenomena and will be validated using empirical data. These models will then be used in the prototypes' performance optimization phase. Finally, the NEPCM samples will be analysed using techniques such as hot disk and DSC/TGA to evaluate their morphological properties.</p>
Requested budget	1,472,120 €
Assessment	The EFESTO proposal was not selected to progress beyond the first stage of the evaluation.

SALTOpower YR Radia El Cadi will be submitting an ERC Starting Grant proposal under the call identifier ERC-2026-StG, which is expected to open in July 2025, after the description in Table 4.3. Assessment results are expected by May 2026.

Table 4.3: Summary of ERC Starting Grant application by Radia El Cadi (UEvora YR)

Call	
Applicant name	Radia AIT EL CADI
Title	“MS-DINAMIC”: Design and experimental validation of an upgraded molten salt INfrastructure for experimental Assessment and technology transfer activities on Carnot Batteries: alternative system composition, system Modeling, experimental validation, Competitiveness assessment
Abstract	<p>The research proposal aims to design and experimentally validate an upgraded Molten Salt infrastructure for Carnot Batteries. This involves assessing alternative system compositions, developing system models, conducting experimental validations, and performing competitiveness assessments. The primary objective is to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of high-temperature thermal storage components within Carnot batteries. By focusing on these components, the research seeks to advance the technology and facilitate its transfer to practical applications.</p> <p>The research will assess the competitiveness of the technology compared to existing energy storage solutions, providing a critical evaluation of its economic and technical feasibility. The</p>

Call	
	<p>project proposal is expected to deliver several key outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Validated Carnot Battery Configurations: Experimentally validated Carnot Battery configurations will demonstrate improved energy conversion efficiency, reduced thermal losses, and enhanced scalability for industrial and grid-scale applications. Advanced System Models: Detailed thermodynamic models, validated through experimental data, will serve as a robust foundation for optimizing Carnot Battery systems in future applications. Upgraded Experimental Infrastructure: The upgraded infrastructure will be capable of testing a wide range of Carnot Battery configurations, supporting ongoing research and development. Comprehensive Techno-Economic and Business Model Assessment: The techno-economic assessment and business model framework will highlight the most commercially viable configurations, paving the way for large-scale deployment.
Requested budget	€2,182,705.27 (Initial estimated budget; will be updated upon reception of the Heat Pump (HP) and Steam Cycle (SC) quotations, which have already been requested.)
Assessment	The proposal will be submitted for the ERC-2026-StG call, which is expected to be open in July 2025, and the assessment results for step 1 are expected by 5 May 2026.

SALTOpower YR Asma Noura will be submitting an ERC Starting Grant proposal under the call identifier ERC-2026-StG, which is expected to open in July 2025, after the description in Table 4.4. Assessment results are expected by May 2026.

Table 4.4: Summary of ERC Starting Grant application by Asma Noura (UEvora YR)

Call	
Applicant name	Asma Noura
Title	ZEOCAT-H ₂ : "ZEOLite and Carbon CATalysts from Sludge for Hydrogen Production via Advanced Gasification"
Abstract	<p>This project aims to develop a circular and sustainable process for hydrogen production by transforming urban sewage sludge into both catalytic materials and feedstock via solar/renewable-driven gasification process coupled to possible thermal energy storage systems (e.g., molten salts TES systems). The gasification process will be designed to operate at moderate temperatures (around 500-550°C), which ensures compatibility with molten salt systems and helps mitigate potential corrosion issues associated with chlorides present in the sludge.</p> <p>Sludge will be converted into activated carbon and zeolite-based catalysts, which will be doped with zinc (Zn) and/or nickel (Ni) to enhance their efficiency and selectivity in syngas production. These catalysts will then be used in a tailored gasification process to convert the sludge itself into syngas, from which hydrogen will be extracted and purified.</p> <p>The process integrates thermal energy storage based on molten salt, operating around 500-550°C to avoid degradation from chlorides present in sewage sludge. This temperature level will be used for catalyst production stages such as pyrolysis and zeolite synthesis. For the gasification step, which requires significantly higher temperatures (900-1100°C), a dual heat supply strategy will be implemented: solar-derived thermal energy will be supplemented with high-temperature electrical heating. This combined system ensures the flexibility and thermal quality required to reach and sustain the optimal gasification range, thereby enhancing overall energy efficiency and operational reliability.</p>

Call	
	<p>This approach combines waste valorization, catalysis, and thermochemical conversion in a single integrated framework. This dual use of sludge, as both resource and reactant, represents a highly innovative contribution to green hydrogen technologies. The project includes experimental work (catalyst synthesis, gasification trials, hydrogen extraction), supported by detailed material characterization, process optimization, and sustainability assessments (LCA, techno-economic analysis).</p> <p>The expected outcomes are the development of low-cost, sludge-derived catalysts, the demonstration of an efficient hydrogen production process, and the validation of a scalable circular model for waste-to-hydrogen conversion. The project addresses key challenges in waste management, resource recovery, and clean energy production, aligning with EU sustainability goals.</p>
Requested budget	2M€ (Initial estimated budget: Personnel, Equipment & Installation (Gasification reactor, tubular furnace, GC-MS, BET surface area analyzer, etc.), Consumables / Materials (Chemicals (Zn, Ni), sludge samples, lab supplies, catalysts, gases), Travel & Conferences, Dissemination & Publications, Software, Maintenance, IT, Indirect Costs (Overheads),
Assessment	The proposal will be submitted for the ERC-2026-StG call, which is expected to be open in July 2025, and the assessment results for step 1 are expected by 5 May 2026.

SALTOpower YR Imen Amri will be submitting an ERC Starting Grant proposal under the call identifier ERC-2026-StG, which is expected to open in July 2025, after the description in Table 4.5. Assessment results are expected by May 2026.

Table 4.5: Summary of ERC Starting Grant application by Imen Amri (UEvora YR)

Call	
Applicant name	Imen Amri
Title	NEXFUEL: Nano-Emulsion Enabled Thermochemical Conversion of CO ₂ into Renewable Drop-in Fuels
Abstract	<p>The NEXFUEL project introduces a novel thermochemical platform that integrates nanotechnology, catalysis, and thermal energy storage systems (molten salts) to convert CO₂-enriched nanoemulsions directly into infrastructure-compatible drop-in fuels. These nanoemulsions are composed of CO₂ sourced from municipal solid waste incineration, bio-oil derived from olive pomace through pyrolysis (500-600°C), and metal-based catalytic nanoparticles (e.g., Ru, Fe, Cu). Acting as self-contained microreactors, the emulsions provide exceptional interfacial surface area and promote efficient mass and heat transfer.</p> <p>At the core of the system is a custom-designed microreactor operating at moderate temperatures (300-500°C), where controlled thermochemical reactions convert nanoemulsions into synthetic diesel, methanol, and other renewable hydrocarbons. The integration of thermal energy storage systems (molten salts) (280-600°C) ensures round-the-clock process stability. Additionally, the platform supports optional solar-driven redox cycles (operating at 800-1000°C) to enhance CO₂ splitting and syngas generation. To achieve and maintain these high temperatures, the system will incorporate electrical heating technology alongside solar thermal input, providing flexible, high-grade thermal energy that expands the overall efficiency and operational range of the fuel production process</p> <p>Expected Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration of significantly enhanced CO₂ conversion rates and fuel selectivity using nanoemulsion-based feedstocks. • Quantitative understanding of how nanoconfinement and interfacial phenomena accelerate thermochemical reactions. • Development of scalable, modular reactor architectures suited for both decentralized and industrial-scale CO₂ utilization.

Call	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishment of benchmarks for solar-to-fuel conversion efficiency and lifecycle carbon reduction. Validation of the technical and economic viability of integrating municipal CO₂ sources with renewable fuel synthesis, supporting a circular carbon economy.
Requested budget	1.5 M (Personal cost, Major equipment including microreactor system assisted with high temperature induction furnace and coupled with micro-GC, pyrolysis reactor, and consumables like pyrolysis feedstock, surfactants, catalysts).
Assessment	The proposal will be submitted for the ERC-2026-StG call, which is expected to be open in July 2025, and the assessment results for step 1 are expected by 5 May 2026.

4.2 ERC Synergy Grant application

In preparation of an application to a ERC Synergy Grant, SALTOpower Senior Researchers (SR) started a discussion upon the SALTOpower Project Meeting #4 (July 2024) around the following topics:

- who will be the Principal Researcher on ENEA side;
- who will be the Principal Researcher on DLR side;
- what will be the aim of the project: suggestion of beyond SoA concept in D2.1 operationalized in our distributed RI (as of D2.4);
- what will be the complementarity of the different Principal Researchers;
- what will be the complementarity of the different Research Infrastructures: suggestion EMSP enables demonstration of energy system integration;
- inclusion of strong components of services to Industry and technology transfer to market solutions.

Aiming at having a concept ready for application in 2025 Call, a further discussion has been held in December 2024 within SALTOpower Project Steering Committee, with the following conclusions:

- low TRL research contents:
 - use of chlorides as MS media: lead DLR, support ENEA;
 - MS based biorefinery for flexible use of different feedstock (high moisture and low moisture contents through hydrothermal liquefaction or pyrolysis), including possible temperature upgrade by means of chlorides (to say 700°C): lead ENEA, support DLR IFF;
- research infrastructure:
 - upgrade EMSP for the use of chlorides: lead UEvora, support DLR + ENEA
- next steps:
 - UEvora: send list of steel grades in MS side of HPS2 and NEWSOL loops (Paula martins will send this within this week to DLR);
 - Meeting with ENEA on the thermochemistry side of the proposal.

In this meeting, and stemming from the fact the consortium background is anchored, to a good extend, on research infrastructures supporting activities on TRL 4-6, which renders difficult to present a good proposal on lower TRL levels, as seems to be a requirement for ERC Synergy grants, an alternative plan has also been discussed. Such a plan would entail, as an alternative, the preparation of a concept for a UEvora lead application to a HORIZON EUROPE WIDERA Excellence Hub Call.

This alternative plan has already been exploited:

- upon contact with SALTOpower Project Officer, who confirmed this possibility upon due justification in deviations to the original plan;

- upon contact with the Portuguese National Contact Point, validating the possibility of using an Excellence Hub proposal as a corollary of SALTOpower activities in WPs 2, 3 and 4 to the Widening institution, informing that a Call is foreseen for 2027.

A final decision on which proposal to develop within the framework of SALTOpower will be taken by the Consortium, upon discussion in the SALTOpower Project Meeting #6 (May'2025) and duly reported and documented in the project final report.

5. SPIN-OFF FACILITY

Standing as a support measure aiming at providing YR with an entrepreneurial path for their careers, seeking a possible commercial exploitation or research results, the SALTOpower Spin-Off facility provided both Candidate and Young Researchers with guidance and support in the creation of Spin-off companies. Considering the different aspects pertaining to this process, materials on legal, financial, specific measures for IP protection (patents or other forms of protection) and fiscal aspects, besides an overview of the framework of Spin-offs at their different development (and financing) stages have been prepared in an internal cooperation, at the Widening institution, with the Innovation and Entrepreneurial office of the University of Évora (DIC2E).

A first seminar on the Spin-Off facility took place in the 3rd SALTOpower meeting (Évora, 15.11.2023). In this Seminar, a presentation on “Empowering Entrepreneurship: The Role of Spin-off Facilities” has been presented, including topics such as:

- Innovation stages - from Idea to Monetization - Ideation, Validation, Protection, Market;
- Ideation - identifying a problem, its solution and whether it has a competitive advantage;
- Validation - proof of concept (a demonstration to validate an idea), prototyping and usability test, market pool (potential customer base) and business model;
- Protection - different ways of protecting an idea or technology: patent, utility model, brands, design, trade secrets and copyright (differences between them were explained by using an umbrella with different innovations as an example);
- Market - public support to investment (how to find them), training in “elevator pitch” and how to approach Venture Capitals and Business Angels, and exit strategy for investors.

Figure 5.1: Exemplary contents of Spin-Off facility materials.

Aiming at mapping the available resources, both internally and in the Widening region, supporting the different stages of a spin-off creation, UEvora developed an innovation assets matrix to be continuously updated throughout the project and enabling the identification of gaps and needed improvements.

Action

HR	Creators Product Managers Market Researchers	Prototype Developers Business Analysts UX Designers	Legal Advisors (IP) Lawyers	Marketing Team Sales Team (PR) Specialists
Funding	Research	Workshops	Legal Fees	BA and VC
Tools	Brainstorming Communication	Survey and FeedBack Prototype tools	Legal project manag. Doc. manag. system	Social media management
Facilities	Office/Workspace Labs	Office/Workspace Labs	Office/Workspace	Office/Workspace
Networking	Conferences Incubators	Networking events Customer validation	IP Network Associations	Investor Networks

Support resources

Resources

HR	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red
Funding	Green	Green	Orange	Orange
Tools	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange
Facilities	Green	Green	Orange	Orange
Networking	Green	Yellow	Orange	Orange

Support resources

Figure 5.2: Innovation Assets matrix approach in SALTOpower.

In view of exchanging experiences and practice, in this scope, with the filling of such matrix has been requested also to TOP partners (DLR and ENEA) and what needs to be improved or is not available internally.

A final revision of these Innovation Asset Matrices and due discussion on their contents and inter-Consortium cooperation prospects is to be followed upon Project Meeting #6 (May'2025), as to be reported in the final report.

As to the blueprint for the creation of a spin-off, exemplary of the application of the Spin-off facility assets, the Upgraded and Distributed Facility resulting from WP2 will be the object of study. A business model will be developed to enable the operation of the research infrastructure as an independent service provider. This business model will be part of SALTOpower D5.2, as part of the updated exploitation plan for the project results.

Stemming from the internal cooperation in this topic within the Widening institution, a regional funding proposal has already been prepared to enable the research facility as a “demosite incubation space”.

A selection of Spin-off facility related materials will be made publicly available in the project Zenodo repository by the end of the project.

6. LIVING AMENITIES FACILITY

Envisaging a comprehensive approach to the creation of attractiveness conditions for research careers by the Widening partner, the Living Amenities Facility (Task 3.4 of WP3), led by UÉvora, aims at the implementation of a support structure rendering the integration of new researchers in the local context easier and welcoming. The Living Amenities Facility covers the “off work” aspects of what renders attractive the Widening context: access to an Excellence Research Infrastructure developing cutting-edge research, having the conditions to feel integrated and able to self-establish with a high life quality standard.

Initially, this facility was based on the creation of a “pre-paid Pass”, but given the legal and administrative obstacles in terms of its financial management faced with the implementation of the Living Amenities Pass (Milestone 12) - how to implement and charge for the pass, who/which department would provide the administrative support to the pass, how to establish further protocols for discounts, and legal constraints related to Public Procurement - the scope of Task 3.4 and MS12 was changed to shift it towards the actions being undertaken to mitigate this problem.

One of the WP3 identified risks was related to Living Amenities WP3 [T3.4]: “Living Amenities pass has no subscriptions”, and a possible response strategy, following D1.1 Quality Assurance and Risk Mitigation Plan, was to reduce it by revising the contents of the Pass and outreach for discounts, or possibly revision of concept to "networking" and/or "welcoming package" concept.

As this risk became an Issue, as the implementation of a Living Amenities Pass faced obstacles, mitigation procedures were taken.

The contingency plan was to foster an alternative solution based on information supply only, and, as a result, a simplified solution was established by the consortium:

- implementing and expanding the Living Amenities assets available on the project website (map with marked points of interest, cultural agenda, useful contacts, etc.);
- implementing a “Mentoring Initiative” scheme, aiming to introduce the city/region and the aforementioned assets helping the newcomers - mentees - to arrive and settle in the region by residents - volunteer mentors (on a first approach, considering researchers and technicians at UÉvora).

- **Living in... on the SALTOpower website**

On the project website, <https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/>, the menu “Careers” (Figure 6.1) includes the Living Amenities section that was designated as “Living in Alentejo”, the Widening partner region. The TOP partners are considering the possibility of a similar section for their regions.

The concept of the Living Amenities Facility was developed in the project meetings, and the “Living in Alentejo” section on the SALTOpower website is implemented by the Widening partner UÉvora. All assets on the website are translated into English and the partners' languages, Portuguese, Italian, and German.

“Living in Alentejo” (<https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/living-in-alentejo/>) refers to the Alentejo region, where the University of Évora is located. The Alentejo is the region located in the centre-south of Portugal, and though it has the largest extension, it occupies around a third of the national territory - it is one of the least populated. The Alentejo (the name derives from ‘beyond the Tagus River’) is known for its rural landscape, and historical and cultural heritage. Évora, the main city, is a UNESCO World Heritage Site.

Figure 6.1: “Living in Alentejo” on the SALTOpower website.

In this website section (Figure 6.2), videos about the region and the Renewable Energies Chair (UÉvora), a map with points of interest was developed (with the contribution of all partners to define which are the main points of interest to be highlighted), a calendar of activities and events in the city of Évora and surrounding area, a link to the University’s welcome guide, a list of useful contacts, and a small dictionary of useful English words translated into Portuguese, are

available.

Figure 6.2: “Living in Alentejo” on the SALTOpower website.

- **Mentoring Initiative**

The SALTOpower Mentoring Program is active on the project website (<https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/mentoring-program/>, Figure 6.3).

It offers the opportunity to be a volunteer mentor who will help mentees to arrive and settle in the region, in activities outside of work, like finding a house or processing documents. To sign up for the program as a mentor or as a mentored, it is just necessary to fill out a form available on the SALTOpower website, and mentors and mentees will be paired by their schedule availability, language and interests. These forms are available in English, Portuguese, Italian and German (Figures 6.3 to 6.6).

Figure 6.3: “Mentoring Program” on the SALTOpower website.

SALTOpower Mentoring Program

This is a form for those who want to be a **mentor** in the SALTOpower program.

A mentor is someone who helps those who come to Évora to support them in their day-to-day lives, with regard to services, transportation, mobility, etc.

If you are interested, fill in this form.

Name *

A sua resposta _____

E-mail *

A sua resposta _____

Short bio *

A sua resposta _____

What languages do you speak? *

A sua resposta _____

What is your availability? (Days/hours) *

A sua resposta _____

Send us a photo *

Carregue 1 ficheiro suportado. Máximo de 10 MB.

[Adicionar ficheiro](#)

**I am aware that the data I provide voluntarily and anonymously is the responsibility of the SALTOpower project coordinator (lead researcher: Dr. Pedro Horta) and will be stored until the end of the project (2025), in a folder with restricted access to SALTOpower partners. *
Contacts will only be shared exclusively with SALTOpower partners (UEvora, ENEA and DLR) if authorization to do so is given.**

Yes

Enviar
Limpar formulário

Figure 6.4: Mentors form.

SALTOpower Mentoring Program

This is a form for those who want to be a **mentored** in the SALTOpower program.

A mentored is someone who will have a mentor that give support in you day-to-day lives, with regard to services, transportation, mobility, etc.

If you are interested in being a mentored, fill in this form.

Name *

A sua resposta _____

E-mail *

A sua resposta _____

Short bio *

A sua resposta _____

What languages do you speak? *

A sua resposta _____

What are your main needs? (support to find a home, get to know the city, go to a public service, etc). *

A sua resposta

Send us a photo *

Carregue 1 ficheiro suportado. Máximo de 10 MB.

[Adicionar ficheiro](#)

Who do you prefer to be your mentor? (Write the name of someone on our website Mentoring Program) *

A sua resposta

I am aware that the data I provide voluntarily and anonymously is the responsibility of the SALTOpower project coordinator (lead researcher: Dr. Pedro Horta) and will be stored until the end of the project (2025), in a folder with restricted access to SALTOpower partners. Contacts will only be shared exclusively with SALTOpower partners (UÉvora, ENEA and DLR) if authorization to do so is given. *

Yes

Enviar Limpar formulário

Figure 6.5: Mentoreds form.

<p>Quero ser mentor</p> <p>Clica aqui</p>	<p>Voglio essere un mentore</p> <p>Clicca qui</p>	<p>Ich möchte ein Mentor sein</p> <p>Klicken Sie hier</p>
<p>Quero ser mentorado</p> <p>Clica aqui</p>	<p>Voglio essere affiancato da un mentore</p> <p>Clicca qui</p>	<p>Ich möchte einen Mentor</p> <p>Klicken Sie hier</p>

Figure 6.6: “Mentoring Program” on the SALTOpower website translated to Portuguese, Italian, and German.

For the number of registered mentors and mentees, a KPI of 5/15/30 (good/very good/excellent) registrations was defined (maintaining the KPI initially set for Living Amenities Pass subscriptions). At the moment, there are 5 registrations: 2 mentors and 3 mentored (Figures 6.7 and 6.8).

Figure 6.7: Registered Mentors.

Figure 6.8: Registered Mentorees.

- **Further activities**

In addition to possible updates to the “Living in...” sections on the SALTOpower website and the continuation of the mentoring initiative with further registrations and matches, other activities have been planned, such as “round a coffee” social events and cultural visits. These activities will be organised by UÉvora to integrate and improve the experience of researchers or other staff coming to UÉvora, if these newcomers come (particularly if for long-term stays), either during the project period or beyond it, as this good practice is now established within the team.

During the last Project Meeting and Fast-Track School, in Évora (February 2025), a short walk between the venue and the bus to visit the UÉvora Research Infrastructure, one of the mentors showed a group of participants and partners some of Évora's monuments and views of the city (Figure 6.9).

Figure 6.9: Visit to Évora.

7. IMPACT

Besides the impacts produced with the aforementioned support measures on Capacity Building, ERC, Spin-off and Living Amenities facilities, satisfaction surveys among the researchers engaged in SALTOpower activities have been conducted to better assess individual viewpoints.

The survey mentioned in section 3.2, was applied not only to CYR and YR, but also to Senior Researchers and Technical/Administrative staff, with a total of 11 answers. Table 7.1 presents some of the more relevant questions answered by the SALTOpower team.

Table 7.1: SALTOpower team answers to the satisfaction survey (M25).

Question	Classification (out of 5)
How satisfied are you with SALTOpower research?	4,09
How satisfied are you with the support for career development at your institution?	3,27
How satisfied are you with the SALTOpower Research Infrastructure?	4,18
How satisfied are you with the SALTOpower team?	4,82
How satisfied are you with SALTOpower in general?	4,18

During the period of the project, visits to the Research Infrastructure were also promoted (apart from the visits during SALTOpower events, e.g. FTS, Regional Specialization Forum, Energy Strategy Symposium), with visitors from the Academia, Policy and Industry to EMSP - Évora Molten Salt Platform (University of Évora).

Some of the visits that took place were from the CEO and other DLR members (9 visitors) in March'2023; from the CIAIE - Iberian Centre for Research in Energy Storage (Fundecyt-PCTEX) (25 visitors that were attendees of a vocational training teachers in the area of renewable energies) in July'2023; from the Polytechnic Institute of Portalegre (25 visitors, in the framework of the Kickoff Meeting of the European project PYRAGRAF) in July'2023; from DGEG - General Directorate of Energy and Geology (3 visitors) in April'2024 (Figure 7.2); from ACWA Power, in the scope of a collaboration with GlassPoint (1 visitor) in January'2025; and from CTE - Training Centre for the Energy Transition (10 visitors) in March'2025.

Figure 7.2: DGEG visit to EMSP (April 2024).

All public content of SALTOpower is available on the project website, www.saltopower.uevora.pt, including news, deliverables, scientific publications, FTS materials, etc., and it had, by M29, 1556 visitors (4128 visualisations). From these publications, the video materials (SALTOpower video and FTS presentations) are available on SALTOpower YouTube and have 629 visualisations, while scientific papers and FTS presentations are available on SALTOpower Zenodo and have a total of 1921 downloads.

8. RELATED PLANS (FOLLOWING PM² METHODOLOGY)

Deliverables Acceptance Plan

The management of the formal customer's acceptance of project deliverables (responsibilities, activities and the criteria for the deliverables acceptance) is described in the *Deliverables Acceptance Plan*. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Project Description of Action

The *Project Description of Action* includes the project Work Plan and captures all types of resource requirements, schedules and effort/costs foreseen for the deliverables acceptance activities. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

The Project documents will be stored in a shared drive located on the DLR server in Germany. The access will be granted by that partner, and each user will have a different access according to their profile, role and responsibility in the project.

The Project Steering Committee (PSC) will have access and editing permissions to all folders in the drive. The Project Core Team (PCT) will have editing access to respective WP folders and reading access to the remaining ones. The Project Support Team (PST) will have reading access to WP folders, and finally, the Project Owner (PO) may have reading access to all folders, including legal documents.

In each folder, the latest PDF and Word versions of each document will be available, and the previous versions shall be conserved in a separate folder named [versions] until the end of the project.

At the end of the project, each partner will make a copy of the shared folder to be stored in their own organisation's drive, and this must be kept following internal organisational procedures.

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
1	Project folder	
2	Project Description of Action (Part A) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part A).pdf>	Project folder
3	Project Description of Action (Part B) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part B).pdf>	Project folder
4	Deliverables acceptance Checklist <[29.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Checklist.SALTOPOWER.10-02-2023.v1.0>	Project Folder
5	D3.1 Fast-Track School materials <SALTOPOWER_D_3_1_FTS-materials_31-01-2025_v1>	Project Folder